

Van Order Project, Henry County (41.48446, -83.90940)

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Van Order Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source which prevents approximately 0.3 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. The Project pools appear to be functioning as intended, holding water during the wet season (late winter to spring) and drying in summer and fall. Capacity of soils to sorb phosphate appears to be increasing across the Project across years, suggesting potential to capture and hold relatively large loads of phosphorus when water/nutrient inputs are present.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 5 acres of restored wetland and consists of eight isolated wetland pools. Pools 1 - 7 receive flow only from surface water runoff, while the southernmost pool (Pool 8) might receive flood water from a nearby agricultural ditch. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event where surface water runoff is delivered to the pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmland Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
5 acres	0.3 lbs	10 ± 5 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in similar isolated wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Assess parcel footprint for the ability to capture tile drain, stream, or ditch water inputs, in addition to precipitation, in order to optimize nutrient input potential (i.e., connectivity).

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.